

Sharing Info

Akun Student Turnitin No Repository Terbaru (New)

The image displays two side-by-side screenshots of the Turnitin student homepage. Both pages show the Turnitin logo, navigation tabs (All Classes, Enroll in a Class, What is Plagiarism?, Citation Help), and a 'NOW VIEWING: HOME' section. The left screenshot is for a student at Universiti Putra Malaysia, Faculty of Educational Studies, with a class ID of 21707872 and class name 'GREduc 2019'. The right screenshot is for a student at Universitas Islam Indonesia, Ahwal Al-Syakhshiyah, with a class ID of 19983066 and class name 'Skripsi Mahasiswa'. Both pages feature a prominent red 'SUBSCRIBE NOW' button. A large, stylized watermark text 'UPDATE INFO BARU AKUN TURNITIN STUDENT NO REPOSITORY' is overlaid across both screenshots. The browser address bar shows the URL 'turnitin.com/s_home.asp?login=1&s...'. The Windows taskbar at the bottom indicates the date is 21/11/2019 and the time is 13:26.

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